

تفعيل تكنولوجيا التعليم
Activating EdTech

Activating Educational Technology Sprint 2 Report

February 17-21, 2019, Amman

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Activating EdTech, <http://tiny.cc/ActivatingEdTech>, March 2019

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Information about the Activating EdTech and our outputs can be found at <http://tiny.cc/ActivatingEdTech>.

Our outputs are archived here <https://zenodo.org/communities/aet/>.

تفعيل تكنولوجيا التعليم
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Table of contents

Project Overview	4
Sprint 1 Recap	4
Sprint 2 Overview	5
Outputs of Sprint 2	5
Output 1: Outline for Edtech Strategy	5
Output 2: School Visit	5
Output 3: Three Units and three cross-cutting Chapters set up to take forward key aspects of work over the next six weeks	5
Planned Agenda	7
Changes in Agenda	9
Digital Service Design Standards	9

Project Overview

Activating Edtech aims to develop working habits and processes for the incorporation of evidence into Edtech related decision making at all levels of the Jordanian Ministry of Education. The project aims to instil the principles of collaboration, iteration and the incorporation of research by emulating these principles itself. The project, therefore, deliberately avoids a top-down and rigid approach in favour of a more communal and flexible one. As a result, the project's interim outputs and schedule are in constant flux, however, while still ensuring productivity and quality and with a clear final project output in mind.

The first phase of the project is set up around 3 Sprints, defined as being intense periods of work with the Activating Edtech Team. The Team is made up of various stakeholders from within and without the MoE. During these sprints, the Team discusses and produces outputs, and agrees upon the work to be done before and during the next sprint.

Sprint 1 Recap

The first sprint took place from January 21-24th 2019 and gathered 20 Ministry and non-Ministry stakeholders (hereafter referred to as 'the Edtech Team') to explore how to use evidence to inform decision making in EdTech. The sprint emulated the adaptive management approach it is aiming to instil in the MoE. While there was initial resistance to the approach, as many believed it lacked direction, there was more acceptance to the ambiguity as the sprint progressed.

Sprint 2 Overview

The second sprint took place from Feb 17 – 21st 2019. Revolving around a more concrete deliverable (outlining an Edtech Strategy), the Sprint began with a discussion of the reports developed by the working groups and then continued to discuss what the Edtech Strategy should entail.

Outputs of Sprint 2

Output 1: Outline for Edtech Strategy

- An outline was completed for an Edtech strategy, including the following areas:
 - Vision and Goals
 - Principles
 - Key areas:
 - Students learning with Edtech
 - Professional learning
 - Supporting Systems
 - Equity, Inclusion and Safety
 - Cross-cutting Areas:
 - Infrastructure
 - Curriculum
 - Quality

Output 2: School Visit

- Two members of the team visited a school to conduct user interviews with teachers.
- The visit was eye-opening to one of the members, who had never visited a public school before, and insisted on school visits be conducted personally before designing policy.

Output 3: Three Units and three cross-cutting Chapters set up to take forward key aspects of work over the next six weeks

- Toward the end of the sprint workshop, the Edtech Team formed 3 Units and 3 Chapters to explore different elements of EdTech:
 - Unit 1: ICT in the Classroom

The squad will explore the use of ICT in the classroom, and look into Geogebra as a case study, conducting a micro-experiment in schools.

- Unit 2: Teacher Professional Development
 - Review existing TPD programs to identify their quality
 - Review google sheet listing programs from 2006 - 2016 they can use but they need to add new/planned ones
- Unit 3: Systems Strengthening
 - Interested in conducting an online survey of teachers, students parents and principals about the situation in the classroom
- Chapter 1: Documentation
- Chapter 2: Technology
- Chapter 3: Research
- The units will meet weekly, and work on their Kanban boards to plan their work.

Planned Agenda

	Sun	Mon	Tue	Wed	Thu
Morning Session (9:00-11:30) <i>Learning Module</i>	Kick-off presentation (30 mins) Working Group Presentations	Learning module: Stakeholder mapping analysis Trust-building exercise	Learning module: Models of student-centred teaching and learning	Learning module: Results-based management and the use of indicators	Arrangements for the walking period.
11:30-12:30		Applied Module	Applied Module	Applied Module	
12:30-1:30	Lunch				
Afternoon Session (1:30-3:30) <i>Applied Module</i>	Discussion of outline for roadmap and strategy; assignment of areas (mainly according to working groups)	Applied Module	Applied Module	Applied Module	F reporting out
Late Afternoon Session (3:30-4:30) <i>(Optional)</i>	ICT practice sessions (optional) : Google Docs, Zotero, Kanban, GeoGebra, Flickr/CC Facilitator Meeting				

Each day of the sprint would be divided into three parts:

- Learning Module (Morning):** During this period, the team is introduced to a new exercise/concept and conducts activities surrounding the learning objectives.

تفعيل تكنولوجيا التعليم
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- **Applied Module (Afternoon):** This module is focused on the collective development of the project outputs. It is also dedicated to applying the newly learned concepts into practice through the outputs, which include:
 - Roadmap and Initial Policy - *2 groups will be working on this topic*
 - Refinement and application of indicators - *1 group*
 - Teacher support plan - *1 group*
- **Optional ICT Practice (Late Afternoon):** Those who need support or would like to learn more about specific collaboration or Edtech tools can remain for the last session, and explore interactive activities with EdTech and/or have access to technical support.

Changes in Agenda

In the spirit of iteration, the Sprint's agenda changed as a response of the team's progress, flow and suggestions.

	Sun	Mon	Tue	Wed	Thu
Morning Session (9:00-12:30)	Kick-off presentation (30 mins) Working Group Presentations	Stand-up	Stand-up	Stand-up	Stand-up
		Discussion of outline for Policy and Roadmap	Presentation of group "pillars" Digital Service Design Standards	Consolidating policy document outline School Visits	Arrangements for the walking period.
12:30-1:30	Lunch				
Afternoon Session (1:30-3:30)	Working Group Discussions	Discussion of outline for Policy and Roadmap	Google Contacts and Zotero User stories + Voting	Consolidating policy document outline <i>continued</i>	Arrangements for the walking period <i>continued</i>
Late Afternoon Session (3:30-4:30) (Optional)	ICT practice sessions (optional): Google Docs, Zotero, Kanban, GeoGebra, Flickr/CC Facilitator Meeting				